

Supplemental File S1

Table 1. $P(\text{corr})$ values generated from OPLS-DA performed on peaks integral values of four major biomarkers of bovine milk and related cross-validated R^2Y and Q^2 coefficients with P -value from random permutation test based on 1000 permutations processed for five different pairs in relation to the percentage of adulteration.

Pair of groups ¹	$p(\text{corr})$				Cross-validated R^2Y , Q^2 coefficients and P -value from random permutation test		
	N-acetyl carbohydrates	Unknown compound	Orotate	Citrate	R^2Y	Q^2	P -value
Caprine 100% - Bovine 100%	-0.9959	-0.8262	-0.9487	-0.8163	0.838	0.811	< 0.001
Caprine 100% - Bovine 1%	-0.3365	-0.1365	0.4464	0.8614	0.0104	-0.0948	not significant
Caprine 100% - Bovine 5%	-0.8828	-0.3906	-0.1818	0.0779	0.628	0.54	< 0.001
Caprine 100% - Bovine 10%	-0.9562	-0.5899	-0.3920	0.0151	0.752	0.704	< 0.001
Bovine 5% - Bovine 10%	-0.8756	-0.3544	-0.3014	-0.064	0.528	0.404	< 0.001

¹Each group contained: n = 23

Table 2. Arithmetic mean, standard error, minimum and maximum of peaks integral values of *N*-acetyl carbohydrates.

Groups ¹	Arithmetic mean	Standard error	Minimum	Maximum
Caprine 100%	0.045	0.004	0.012	0.090
Bovine 1%	0.047	0.004	0.024	0.088
Bovine 5%	0.077	0.003	0.048	0.110
Bovine 10%	0.115	0.006	0.075	0.182
Bovine 100%	1.101	0.074	0.586	1.811

¹Each group contained: n = 23

Table 3. The evaluation of utility of N-acetyl carbohydrate signal for the detection of caprine milk adulterated by bovine milk by blind test according to the formula mentioned by Dalabasmaz et al. (2019).

Pairs of groups ¹	Correct Evaluation		Wrong Evaluation		Accuracy (%)
	TP ²	TN ³	FP ⁴	FN ⁵	
Caprine 100% - Bovine 100%	5	5	0	0	100
Caprine 100% - Bovine 5%	3	5	2	0	80
Caprine 100% - Bovine 10%	5	5	0	0	100

¹Each group contained: n = 5

²True positive

³True negative

⁴False positive

⁵False negative